

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
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2 Executive summary

A primary objective of WP7 is to detect and understand drivers of extreme events and ecosystem regime shifts in the Atlantic Ocean. In this deliverable, we focus on marine heatwaves, ocean biogeochemical extremes and compound events. Our findings indicate that the primary driver of surface marine heatwaves in the subtropical Atlantic and mid-to-high latitudes is an anomalous transfer of heat from the atmosphere to the surface ocean. In contrast, in the tropics, ocean interior processes are more important. Additionally, increased ocean temperatures play a key role in driving surface ocean acidity ($[H^+]$) extremes, particularly in the subtropics, where enhanced ocean heat uptake is the dominant factor triggering such events. The alignment of processes driving both marine heatwaves and ocean acidity extremes in the subtropics makes these regions hotspots for compound marine heatwaves and ocean acidity extremes, which are expected to become more frequent in the future. The air-sea CO_2 uptake decreases locally by up to 30% during marine heatwaves. Our analysis also reveals that compound marine heatwaves and low net primary productivity extremes (NPPX) are particularly common in low-to mid-latitude regions. These events are linked to nutrient limitations that reduce phytoplankton growth, resulting in frequent compound MHW-NPPX extremes. Lastly, we show that triple compound extremes are prevalent across the South Atlantic during El Niño phases, highlighting the importance of ENSO-driven predictability for marine heatwaves in these regions.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

Marine heatwaves and ocean biogeochemical extremes can have far-reaching impacts on marine species, including shifts in species distribution, loss of biodiversity, the collapse of foundation species and declines in fisheries and cultural values. The increasing occurrence of compound ocean extreme events has emerged as a particular threat. However, the characteristics and drivers of extreme and compound extreme events in the Atlantic Ocean remain largely unexplored.

Within the AtlantECO project, we have focused on analysing past (and future) changes in ocean physical and biogeochemical extreme events as well as their underlying drivers through statistical analysis of physical, chemical and biological (satellite-based) data products as well as through dedicated Earth system model experiments. The key findings are summarised and discussed in this report. To date, 10 manuscripts related to the findings of this deliverable have been published or submitted to peer-reviewed journals.

4 Work carried out and main results achieved

4.1 Marine heatwaves in the Atlantic Ocean

We have investigated the drivers of surface marine heatwaves (MHWs) in the Atlantic Ocean using daily-mean output of temperature tendency terms from a comprehensive fully coupled Earth system model to quantify the main local processes leading to the onset and decline of surface MHWs in different seasons (Figure 1). Marine heatwaves are particularly intense in the western boundary currents of the North and Southern Atlantic. Our analysis indicate that the onset of MHWs in the subtropics and mid-to-high latitudes is primarily driven by net ocean heat uptake associated with a reduction of latent heat loss in all seasons, increased shortwave heat absorption in summer and reduced sensible heat loss in winter, dampened by reduced vertical mixing especially in summer. In the equatorial Atlantic, MHWs are associated with reduced ocean heat uptake and driven by reduced vertical mixing and diffusion. This study has been published in *Frontiers in Climate* (Vogt et al. 2022).

Figure 1: Simulated drivers of marine heatwaves in the Atlantic Ocean. Simulated patterns of the four most important heat and temperature tendency terms averaged over the 500-yr preindustrial control simulation

(a,d,g,j), during the onset phase of MHWs (b,e,h,k) and during the decline phase of marine heatwaves (c,f,i,l). The patterns during the onset and decline phase were obtained by averaging daily surface tendency anomalies of each term over all onset and decline days of MHWs, respectively. Implied temperature changes are also given. Figure modified from Vogt al. (2022).

We also contributed to the understanding of the unprecedented sea surface temperatures records in the North Atlantic in 2023. Average temperatures in the region (0° - 60° N, 0° - 80° W) reached levels exceeding four standard deviations above the 1980-2011 baseline during parts of July and September 2023, with an annual average $\sim 0.23^{\circ}$ C higher than in 2022. We found that the pattern of Atlantic warming is consistent with the negative phase of the North Atlantic Oscillation, which was indeed strongly negative from mid-April to mid-May and most of July 2023. The concentration of the 2023 warming in near-surface waters suggests that upper ocean stratification, possibly modulated by large-scale climate modes, may have played an important role in preventing the excess heat absorbed by the ocean from being effectively distributed downward, resulting in enhanced surface warming. In addition to these mostly natural drivers, the ocean is estimated to have absorbed about 91% of the excess heat associated with global warming, causing an average warming of the upper 2000m of the global ocean. Thus, it is very likely that climate change has contributed to the intensity and widespread coverage of the 2023 MHW. Although this analysis was not planned for this deliverable, the urgency and high media attention surrounding the North Atlantic marine heatwave event prompted us to investigate this further. The findings are discussed in Capotondi et al. (under revisions), a paper currently under revision *Communications Earth & Environment*.

In an additional study published in *Science Advances* (Cael et al. 2024), we have tested if state-of-the-art Earth system models are able to reproduce extreme ocean temperature statistics in the Atlantic Ocean. We show that annual maxima of detrended anomalies in daily mean sea surface temperatures over 39 years of satellite observations are described excellently by the generalised extreme value distribution. We also show that CMIP6 Earth system models can reproduce the satellite-based distribution and its parameter's spatial patterns, increasing the confidence in their marine heatwave projections. We additionally find that maximum sea surface temperature will strongly increase under both the SSP1-26 and SSP5-85 scenario and that these changes are mainly due to mean SST increases, slightly reinforced by SST seasonality increases, especially in the tropical Atlantic Ocean. Exceptions of these general trends are the Southern Ocean and the North Atlantic, where future trends in SST are sometimes negative.

We also investigated the impacts of MHWs on regional air-sea CO₂ exchange using thirty global observation-based air-sea CO₂ flux datasets from 1990 to 2019 (Figure 2). Our analysis shows that the CO₂ uptake is reduced during MHWs in the subpolar North Atlantic and the mid latitudes of the North and South Atlantic. Locally the air-sea CO₂ exchange can decrease by up to 30% during marine heatwaves. Significant changes are largely absent in the tropical Atlantic Ocean. We found the air-sea CO₂ flux response to MHWs to be mainly driven by changes in the partial pressure of CO₂. Two competing mechanisms can alter this partial pressure during MHWs: a thermal effect and a non-thermal carbon effect. In the mid-latitudes of the Atlantic, the thermal effect dominates, whereas in the tropics the non-thermal DIC effect often dominates. This study is currently under revisions in *Geophysical Research Letters* (Li et al. in revisions).

Figure 2: Marine heatwave impacts on sea-air CO₂ exchange. a) Observation-based sea-air CO₂ flux anomalies during MHWs averaged over the 1990-2019 period and across all observation-based products. Results are only shown for regions where all six observation-based CO₂ products have data. The grey dashed lines indicate the regions shown in panel b) and hatching indicate regions, where the anomalies are not statistically different. b) Climatological mean sea-air CO₂ flux, mean sea-air CO₂ flux during MHWs and mean sea-air CO₂ flux anomalies during MHWs for the years 1990-2019. The bars represent the averages across all observation-based products. The orange points represent the individual 30 observation-based data products. The purple points show the six observation-based pCO₂ products using the average wind product. Figure from Li et al. (in revisions).

4.2 Drivers of high acidity events in Atlantic Ocean

We have assessed and quantified the mechanisms driving ocean acidity extreme (OAX) events using high-frequency output from a fully coupled Earth system model of all processes that influence the surface ocean temperature and carbon budget, and ultimately of [H⁺] and calcium carbonate mineral saturation state (Ω) anomalies (Figure 3). We revealed that enhanced temperature plays a crucial role in driving [H⁺] extremes, with increased net ocean heat uptake being the dominant driver of the event onset in the subtropics. In the mid-to-high latitudes, decreased downward vertical diffusion and mixing of warm surface waters during summer, and increased vertical mixing with warm and carbon-rich subsurface waters during winter are the main drivers of high [H⁺] extreme event onset. In the tropics, increases in vertical advection of carbon-rich subsurface waters are the primary driver of the onset of high [H⁺] extremes. In contrast, low Ω extremes are driven in most regions by increases in surface carbon concentration due to increased vertical mixing with carbon-rich subsurface waters. The study highlights the complex interplay between heat and carbon anomalies driving OAX events and provides a first foundation for more accurate prediction of their future evolution. The results have been published in *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* (Burger and Frölicher 2023).

Figure 3: Drivers of surface ocean acidity extremes. The contributions to surface [H⁺] extreme event onset (light and dark gray bars) from surface temperature (light and dark orange), surface dissolved inorganic carbon (light and dark green), and surface alkalinity and salinity (light and dark purple). Results are shown separately for hemispheric summer (April to September in the northern hemisphere and October to March in the southern hemisphere; light colors) and hemispheric winter (remaining months; dark colors). Figure taken from Burger and Frölicher (2023).

4.3 Compound extreme events in the Atlantic Ocean

4.3.1 Compound marine heatwaves and high acidity events

We have assessed compound MHW-OAX events, during which marine heatwaves (MHWs) co-occur with ocean acidity extreme (OAX) events. Such events can have larger impacts on marine ecosystems than the individual extremes. Over the period 1982-2019, we find that globally 1.8 in 100 months (or about one out of five present-day MHW months) are compound MHW-OAX event months under a present-day baseline, almost twice as many as expected for 90th percentile extreme event exceedances if MHWs and OAX events were statistically independent. Compound MHW-OAX events are most likely in the subtropics (2.7 in 100 months; 10°–40° latitude) and less likely in the mid-to-high latitudes (0.7 in 100 months; >40° latitude). The likelihood pattern results from opposing effects of temperature and dissolved inorganic carbon on [H⁺]. The likelihood is higher where the positive effect on [H⁺] from increased temperatures during MHWs outweighs the negative effect on [H⁺] from co-occurring decreases in dissolved inorganic carbon. Daily model output from a large-ensemble simulation of an Earth system model is analyzed to assess changes in the MHW-OAX likelihood under climate change. The projected long-term mean warming and acidification trends have the largest effect on the number of MHW-OAX days per year, increasing it from 12 to 265 days per year at 2 °C global warming relative to a fixed pre-industrial baseline. Even when long-term trends are removed, an increase in [H⁺] variability leads to a 60% increase in the number of MHW-OAX days under 2 °C global warming. The paper has been published in *Nature Communications* (Burger et al. 2022).

4.3.2 Compound marine heatwaves and low chlorophyll/net primary productivity events

We provided a first assessment of compound marine heatwaves and low-chlorophyll (LChl) extreme events over the satellite period. Using satellite-based sea surface temperature and chlorophyll concentration estimates, we revealed hotspots of compound MHW and LChl events in the tropical Pacific and the Indian Ocean as well as along the boundaries of the subtropical gyres and around Antarctica. In these regions, compound events that typically last 1 week occur 2 to 4 times more often than expected under the assumption of independence between MHWs and LChl events. The joint exceedance anomalies of SST and chlorophyll are generally low over most of the low-latitudes to mid-latitude ocean (green colors in right panel of Figure 4). high exceedance anomalies are reached in regions exhibiting the most intense MHWs and LChl events, such as in the North Atlantic and in the Southern Ocean. The occurrence of compound MHW and LChl events varies on seasonal to interannual timescales. At the seasonal timescale, most compound events occur

in summer in both hemispheres. At interannual timescales, the frequency of compound MHW and LChl events is strongly modulated by large-scale modes of natural climate variability such as the North Atlantic Oscillation whose negative phase is associated with increased compound event occurrence in the northern North Atlantic (left panel of Figure 4). Our results provide a first understanding of where, when and why compound MHW and LChl events occur in the Atlantic. The results have been published in *Biogeosciences* (Le Grix et al., 2021).

Figure 4: Frequency (% days per year) of compound MHW-NPPX events over 1998-2018. (left) Frequency change in compound event days during the positive phase of the North Atlantic Oscillation (in percent). Grid cells where this frequency change is not statistically relevant remain white. (right) Intensity of compound marine heatwaves and low-chlorophyll events. Mean exceedance anomalies above the 90th and below the 10th percentile thresholds of SST and chlorophyll anomalies, respectively, during compound events. Shown are results over the 1998-2018 period. Figure adapted from Le Grix et al. (2021).

In addition, we have used satellite-based estimates and large ensemble simulations output of two Earth system models to assess the characteristics and potential drivers of compound MHW and low net primary productivity extreme events (NPPX). Satellite-based estimates reveal hotspots of frequent compound MHW-NPPX events in the low to mid latitudes (2-3 times higher than if MHWs and NPPX events were to occur independently; or 7 to 11 days/year) and around Antarctica (Figure 5). The GFDL ESM2M is able to simulate this general pattern in the Atlantic, although it generally overestimates compound event frequency in the low latitudes and underestimates satellite-based compound event frequency in the high latitudes. The CESM2-Le model generally has difficulties simulating this spatial pattern. Both models underestimate the very frequent compound MHW-NPPX events shown in the observations around Antarctica. However, low agreement between the five observation-based estimates (their frequency being as low as 0.5% and as high as 6.5% on average at 75°S) makes it difficult to determine which of the two models better simulates compound events in this region. The frequency patterns can be explained by the drivers of compound events, which vary among the two models and across phytoplankton types. In the low latitudes, MHWs are associated with enhanced nutrient limitation on phytoplankton growth, which results in frequent compound MHW-NPPX events. In the high latitudes, NPPX events in GFDL ESM2M-LE are driven by enhanced light limitation, which rarely co-occurs with MHWs, resulting in rare compound events. In contrast, in CESM2-LE, NPPX events in the high latitudes are driven by reduced nutrient supply, which often co-occurs with MHWs, resulting in relatively frequent compound events. In addition, compound MHW-NPPX events are associated with a relative shift

towards larger phytoplankton in most regions, with potential repercussions on marine ecosystems. The results are published in *Biogeosciences* (Le Grix et al. 2022).

Figure 5: Frequency (% days per year) of compound MHW-NPPX events over 1998-2018. (left) Observation-based corresponding to the mean of the results obtained with five satellite-based estimates of NPP, namely, NOBM-, Standard VGPM, Eppley-VGPM, CbPM-VGPM, and CAFE-VGPM. Earth system model estimates of (middle) GFDL ESM2M-LE and (right) CESM2-LE. Figure adapted from Le Grix et al. (2022).

4.3.3. Compound events in multiple variables

We also investigated the temporal-spatial distribution of compound MHW, high acidity and low chlorophyll events in the equatorial and South Atlantic, using observation-based datasets and reanalysis products (Figure 6). We show that the frequency and intensity of these triple compound events have increased dramatically over the past two decades, peaking in the most recent years. We analysed the drivers of triple compound events for six regions and found that, for the Angola Front and Brazil-Malvinas Confluence regions, these events are associated with a poleward shift of oceanic fronts. In the Agulhas Leakage region, an increase in warmer waters entering from the Indian Ocean leads to compound events. In the western equatorial and subtropical Atlantic, they are caused by changes in the air-sea heat fluxes, while in the eastern equatorial they are caused by a weakening of upwelling. In addition, triple compound events are widespread over the South Atlantic during El Niño events. Since MHWs can often be predicted when they are associated with ENSO, ENSO-related compound events may be predictable too. This paper is currently under review in *Nature Communications* (Rodrigues et al. submitted).

Figure 6: Changes in extreme and compound extreme events in the South Atlantic. Change in the frequency of (a) triple compound events (MHW+LChIX+OAX), (b) marine heatwaves (MHW) + low chlorophyll (LChIX), (c) marine heatwave + high acidity (OAX), (d) marine heatwave (MHW), (e) low chlorophyll (LChIX) and (f) high acidity (OAX) in the equatorial and South Atlantic, represented as the difference between 1999-2008 and 2009-2018. Figure taken from Rodrigues et al. (submitted).

In addition, we have also extended our analysis on the impacts of marine heatwaves and compound events on marine ecosystems. We have conducted an ensemble climate-impact modelling approach that combines a global marine fish model with output from a large ensemble simulations of an Earth system to identify the drivers of severe declines in the total biomass of more than 300 pelagic fish species. Our findings suggest that the most influential drivers of these biomass declines are low net primary productivity events, and not marine heatwaves. In addition, extreme declines in pelagic fish biomass can only be driven by a combination of moderate or extreme anomalies in multiple ocean variables, highlighting the crucial role of compound events in driving severe impacts on pelagic marine ecosystems. The paper has been published in *Global Change Biology* (Le Grix et al. 2023).

5 Conclusion

Contribution to the overall AtlantECO objectives: We have contributed extensively to the overall AtlantECO objectives, especially to the objective OBJ3 “Assess drivers and stressors of change in the Atlantic Ocean”. We expect that additional results will emerge during the remaining months of the project as well as beyond.

Impact and progress beyond state-of-the-art: We have determined for the first time the time and space characteristics of ocean extreme events, such as marine heatwaves, high acidity extremes, low chlorophyll extremes and low oxygen extremes in the Atlantic Ocean. Particularly novel is the assessment of compound extreme events, such as compound marine heatwaves and ocean acidity extremes, or compound marine heatwaves and low chlorophyll events. The recent IPCC AR6 report including the Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate dedicated for the first time a subchapter to ocean extreme events, but compound extreme events have been identified as a knowledge gap. Our results contribute to closing this gap in knowledge. Many results of this deliverable were included in a recent review paper on marine heatwaves, which is currently under review in *Communications Earth and Environment* (Capotondi et al. in revisions).

Lessons learnt and links built: Our analysis suggests that more accurate predictions of ocean extreme and compound events and a better understanding of their potential to trigger regime shifts and tipping points in marine ecosystems require the use of higher-resolution Earth system models with more sophisticated ecosystem representations. Equally important are enhanced observational datasets that incorporate sustained long-term measurements, both in-situ and via remote sensing. Assessing the impacts of such extremes necessitates an interdisciplinary approach that combines biological, physical and chemical insights.

6 References

All references acknowledge AtlantECO:

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